

Mechanical-Quantum Calculations of Base Free, Cationic and Hydrochloride Forms of Semisynthetic Antibiotic Clindamycin

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Abstract:

Structures, topological and vibrational properties of antibiotic clindamycin have been studied as base, protonated and hydrochloride derivatives combining mechanical-quantum calculations with the Scaled Quantum Mechanics Force Field (SQMFF) methodology. Natural bond orbital (NBO) and atoms in molecules (AIM) calculations were performed for those three derivatives of antibiotic in gas phase and aqueous solution. The water effects on the properties of proposed forms were analysed by using the self-consistent reaction field calculations and the IEFPCM model. The hydrochloride species reveals a solvation energy (-301.83 kJ/mol) similar to reported for hydrobromide species of alkaloid

scopolamine. NBO studies for all species evidence two $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions while the AIM calculations reveal different types of H bonds interactions. The hydrochloride form is the most reactive species of clindamycin in both media, as evidence the gap values. In addition, the 174, 177 and 180 normal vibration modes expected for those three forms of antibiotic are completely assigned and its scaled force constants reported for first time.

Keywords: *Clindamycin, molecular structure, FTIR spectrum, force constant, B3LYP calculations.*

Introduction

Clindamycin (7-chloro-lincomycin) is an antibiotic derivative of lincomycin formed by the action bacterium *Streptomyces lincolnensis*. This semisynthetic antibiotic is obtained substituting 7(S)-chloro of the 7(R)-hydroxyl group of lincomycin (Birkenmeyer, & Kagan, 1970; Meyers, Kaplan, & Weinstein, 1969) and used in the treatment of bacterial infections caused by

anaerobic species, protozoan diseases as malaria, acne, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* infections including veterinary medications (Lell, & Kremsner, 2002; Center for Drug Evaluation and Research, n.d.; Daum, 2007; Darley, & MacGowan, 2004; Kahn, Line, & Aiello, 2007). Clindamycin is presented as hydrochloride, phosphate or palmitate according to its forms of administration (Spížek, & Řezanka, 2004; 2017). Ravikumar and Sridhar determined, through X-

ray crystallography studies, the structure of clindamycin hydrochloride as a monohydrate, (2S,4R)-2-(N-{(1S,2S)-2-chloro-1-[(3R,4S,5R,6R)-3,4,5-trihydroxy-6-(methylsulfanyl)perhydropyran-2-yl] propyl} aminocarbonyl)-4-propylpyrrolidinium chloride (Ravikumar, & Sridhar, 2010). So far, structures and properties of free base (FB), protonated (CA) and hydrochloride (HCl) derivatives of clindamycin are not reported nor their complete vibrational assignments. Hence, the purposes of this work are: (i) to study the structures and to predict reactivities and properties of clindamycin and its derivatives and, (ii) to assign the vibrational spectra. Here, FB, CA and HCl of clindamycin in gas phase and water were studied combining the hybrid B3LYP method with the experimental vibrational spectra of clindamycin hydrochloride (Infrared Reference Spectra, n.d.; Brown, & Beyer, 1981; Mohamed, et al., 2017). To carry out those purposes and due to high number of atoms present and to the 180 modes of vibration expected for the hydrochloride form, the 6-31G* basis set was employed (Becke, 1993; Lee, Yang, & Parr, 1988). After that, the vibrational analyses of all forms of clindamycin were accomplished from the harmonic force fields (FF) using the SQMFF approach and the Molvib program (Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). Besides, structural, electronic and topological properties were predicted through the use of NBO (Glendening, et al., 1996) and AIM calculations (Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001; Bader, 1990). Here, the solvation energies were obtained using SCRF calculations with the IEFPCM model (Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981) while the reactivities and their behaviors in both media have been predicted using the frontier orbitals and useful descriptors (Parr, & Pearson, 1983). Finally, the properties obtained for the three forms of clindamycin in different media are compared and their vibrational assignments and scaled force constants are reported.

Mechanical-Quantum Calculations

The theoretical initial structure of clindamycin hydrochloride was that reported crystal structure

for clindamycin hydrochloride (Ravikumar, & Sridhar, 2010), then the chlorine atom was removed from this structure to form the cationic structure and finally, to give rise to the free base, the hydrogen that protonates to nitrogen in the cationic structure was removed. Then, their optimizations were carried out using the Gaussian 09 program with hybrid B3LYP/6-31G* method (Frisch, et al., 2009). For all structures, atomic charges were computed using the Merz-Singh-Kollman (MK) scheme (Besler, Merz Jr., & Kollman, 1990) and the NBO 3.1 and the AIM 2000 programs were used to calculate stabilization energies, bond orders and topological properties (Glendening, et al., 1996; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001; Bader, 1990).

Figure 1. Molecular Structure of Clindamycin Free Base where the Most Prominent Atoms are Presented with Their Numbering According to the Modeled Structure. Definition of the Rings: A1 is the Ring with Six Members while A2 is that with Five Members

The resulting harmonic FFs were evaluated following the SQMFF procedure with the Molvib program (Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). To achieve the assignments were considered potential energy distribution components (PED) $\geq 10\%$ and the resulting SQM. In Figure 1, we can see the molecular structure of free base clindamycin where the most prominent atoms are presented with their numbering according to the modeled structure while the definition of the rings used for the construction of the internal coordinates was as follow, the ring with six members is called A1 while that with five members is A2.

The solvation energies in water were calculated considering radii and non-electrostatic terms with the SMD solvation model (Miertuš, Scrocco, & Tomasi, 1981; Marenich, Cramer, &

Truhlar, 2009), as reported for other species (Rudyk, et al., 2019). Here, the molecular volumes were obtained with the Moldraw program (Ugliengo, 1998) while with the gap values, calculated from the HOMO-LUMO, and different descriptors (μ , χ , η , S , ω , E) were predicted reactivities and behaviours of all forms in both phases following described procedures in the literature (Parr, & Yang, 1989; Parr, Szentpály, & Liu, 1999; Kiyooka, Kaneno, & Fujiyama, 2013).

Results and Discussion

Optimizations in Different Media

The three forms of clindamycin in both phases were optimized using the B3LYP/6-31G* method with C_1 symmetries.

Figure 2. Optimized Molecular Structures of Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Forms of Clindamycin and Atoms Numbering

Figure 2 shows their optimized structures while Table 1 displays a comparison between

geometrical parameters calculated using that method and those determined experimentally by

X-ray diffraction for clindamycin monohydrate
(Ravikumar, & Sridhar, 2010).

Table 1. Comparison of Calculated Geometrical Parameters for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution (AS) with the Corresponding Experimental Values Determined for Clindamycin Hydrochloride

B3LYP/6-31G*							
Parameter	Free Base		Cation		Hydrochloride		Exp. [1]
	Gas	AS	Gas	AS	Gas	AS	
Distance Å							
Cl1-C22	1.843	1.855	1.834	1.852	1.833	1.854	1.844
C22-C25	1.540	1.521	1.523	1.520	1.526	1.521	1.544
C22-C15	1.524	1.540	1.542	1.538	1.543	1.538	1.548
C15-N9	1.455	1.458	1.466	1.458	1.466	1.460	1.480
N9-C19	1.361	1.350	1.333	1.342	1.337	1.348	1.348
C19-O7	1.235	1.247	1.238	1.242	1.241	1.241	1.917
C19-C11	1.535	1.530	1.552	1.537	1.544	1.535	1.555
C11-N8	1.478	1.484	1.524	1.520	1.527	1.531	1.521
C11-C12	1.546	1.550	1.543	1.546	1.535	1.545	1.564
C12-C10	1.544	1.550	1.544	1.541	1.542	1.548	1.559
C10-C13	1.531	1.529	1.531	1.527	1.533	1.526	1.528
C13-N8	1.462	1.470	1.514	1.512	1.511	1.506	1.491
C23-N8	1.454	1.460	1.493	1.492	1.497	1.492	1.492
C10-C17	1.532	1.532	1.535	1.532	1.534	1.532	1.534
C17-C24	1.535	1.534	1.536	1.534	1.536	1.534	1.545
C24-C26	1.532	1.531	1.532	1.531	1.532	1.531	1.542
C15-C14	1.538	1.540	1.546	1.542	1.547	1.542	1.541
C14-C16	1.546	1.545	1.544	1.538	1.562	1.544	1.546
C16-O4	1.412	1.424	1.414	1.426	1.418	1.425	1.420
C16-C18	1.528	1.527	1.532	1.535	1.531	1.525	1.535
C18-O5	1.425	1.428	1.431	1.428	1.441	1.428	1.429
C18-C20	1.549	1.547	1.539	1.545	1.544	1.546	1.540
C20-C21	1.534	1.530	1.539	1.529	1.529	1.535	1.569
C21-O3	1.426	1.435	1.431	1.436	1.426	1.435	1.437
C14-O3	1.432	1.437	1.430	1.435	1.430	1.437	1.432
C21-S2	1.823	1.826	1.819	1.825	1.824	1.827	1.833
C27-S2	1.830	1.829	1.830	1.829	1.829	1.829	1.831
RSMD	0.132	0.130	0.131	0.131	0.131	0.131	
Bond angle (degrees)							
Cl1-C22-C25	108.2	108.1	109.0	108.4	108.3	108.2	109.0
C22-C15-C14	115.7	115.2	115.1	115.2	116.5	115.9	116.1
O3-C14-C16	108.5	107.9	110.3	108.6	116.2	108.3	110.5
C14-C16-O4	112.7	112.4	110.7	107.9	109.0	112.3	111.0
O4-C16-C18	110.4	109.8	111.1	111.7	111.3	110.0	111.6
C18-C20-C21	109.4	109.8	109.8	109.2	107.3	108.7	109.0
C14-O3-C21	112.8	111.9	114.4	113.4	117.6	112.5	113.6
C21-S2-C27	98.6	99.4	100.2	99.7	98.7	99.6	99.0
N9-C19-O7	122.9	122.8	126.0	124.5	125.4	124.2	124.8

C19-C11-N8	107.6	109.7	104.2	106.3	104.1	109.8	110.1
N8-C13-C10	103.8	104.0	104.5	104.3	105.4	103.5	104.2
N8-C11-C12	105.6	105.5	105.3	105.2	105.0	105.2	106.9
C10-C17-C24	114.1	114.0	113.8	113.8	113.8	113.7	114.8
O3-C21-S2	109.1	109.1	108.3	108.8	108.0	108.9	108.0
RMSD	1.3	1.3	1.8	1.6	2.6	1.1	
Dihedral angles (degrees)							
C11-C22-C15-N9	-53.7	-53.2	-56.7	-63.0	-51.1	-54.2	-60.7
N8-C11-C19-O7	-84.5	-76.0	-5.3	-12.0	-0.1	-81.0	0.3
C14-C15-N9-C19	88.5	88.7	137.3	127.4	132.3	85.1	137.2
C15-N9-C19-C11	-168.9	-175.4	-176.6	-178.5	-164.3	-172.9	-177.3
RMSD	44.0	40.6	3.1	7.1	7.5	43.3	

Note: ^aThis work. ^bFrom Ref Ravikumar, K., & Sridhar, B. (2010). RMSD, in bold letters

Comparisons using the root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) values are shown in the same table. In general, the theoretical values agree with the experimental values, although the dihedral angles show higher deviations. In both media, bond distances and angles, small RMSD values around 0.130-0.132 Å and 1.1-2.6°, respectively are observed. In the case of dihedral angles, the free base present greatest deviations in both media, the cationic species in both phases present low RMSD values while the hydrochloride species in the gas phase shows a better correlation. Note that the species that shows low variations in dihedral angle values is the cationic form in aqueous solution; which

would be justified by the substantial volume contraction presented by this species and high dipole moments in both media, while the other two proposed forms show volume expansion, as observed in Table 2.

Solvation Energy, Volume and Dipole Moment

Table 2 shows comparisons of calculated total and relative energies, dipole moments and volume variations (ΔV) for all proposed forms in the two phases using the B3LYP/6-31G* method.

Table 2. Total Energy and Dipolar Moments for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method. Corrected Solvation Energy of All Species of Clindamycin are Also Presented

B3LYP/6-31G*							
	Gas phase			Aqueous solution			
	E (Hartrees)	μ (Debye)	$V(\text{Å}^3)$	E (Hartrees)	μ (Debye)	$V(\text{Å}^3)$	$\Delta V (\text{Å}^3)$
Free base	-2049.2606	0.96	441.0	-2049.3012	1.55	442.6	1.6
Cation	-2049.6561	8.82	444.3	-2049.7550	15.28	437.5	-6.8
Hydrochloride	-2510.0636	7.92	467.5	-2510.1303	14.07	468.4	0.9
Solvation energy (kJ/mol)							
	$\Delta G_u^\#$		ΔG_{nc}		ΔG_c		
Free base	-106.50		30.47		-136.97		
Cation	-259.40		42.43		-301.83		
Hydrochloride	-174.95		36.74		-211.69		

Note: Z.P.V.E, zero point vibrational energy

The analysis shows that CA presents greater μ values in both media than the other ones, as expected for a charged specie while HCl presents lower μ and the neutral form shows a markedly lower value. We see that the values of μ increase for all species in solution, but the base has the lowest value in this medium. Comparisons of magnitudes and orientations of μ vectors for the different forms in both media are observed in Figure 3. For CA, the calculated non-

electrostatic energy (ΔG_{nc}) (Marenich, Cramer, & Truhlar, 2009) has a higher value than the other ones, and therefore this species has higher solvation energy due to its charge. The solvation energy observed for the hydrochloride form (-301.83 kJ/mol) is practically similar to reported for hydrobromide species of alkaloid scopolamine (-309.19 kJ/mol) (Rudyk, et al., 2019).

Figure 3. Comparisons of Magnitudes and Orientations of Dipole Moments Vectors for the Three Species of Clindamycin in Both Media by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Natural Population Atomic NPA, Bond Orders BO and Molecular Electrostatic Potential (MEP) Studies

NPA and MK charges, BO and MEP were investigated for all forms of clindamycin in the

two phases at B3LYP/6-31G* level and the results are presented in Tables 3, 4 and 5, respectively.

Table 3. Atomic MK and NPA Charges for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas and in Aqueous Solution (PCM) by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Atoms	B3LYP/6-31G*											
	Free Base				Cationic				Hydrochloride			
	gas		PCM		gas		PCM		gas		PCM	
	MK	NPA	MK	NPA	MK	NPA	MK	NPA	MK	NPA	MK	NPA
1 Cl	-0.168	-0.104	-0.168	-0.104	-0.154	-0.091	-0.174	-0.100	-0.163	-0.091	-0.165	-0.107
2 S	-0.131	0.242	-0.131	0.242	-0.152	0.212	-0.090	0.251	-0.150	0.238	-0.145	0.241
3 O	0.002	-0.605	0.002	-0.605	-0.111	-0.621	-0.210	-0.614	0.018	-0.613	-0.174	-0.613
4 O	-0.653	-0.772	-0.653	-0.772	-0.636	-0.754	-0.621	-0.748	-0.700	-0.757	-0.640	-0.764
5 O	-0.602	-0.757	-0.602	-0.757	-0.643	-0.779	-0.586	-0.749	-0.670	-0.784	-0.603	-0.759
6 O	-0.455	-0.751	-0.455	-0.751	-0.592	-0.763	-0.522	-0.755	-0.514	-0.807	-0.469	-0.792
7 O	-0.500	-0.674	-0.500	-0.674	-0.467	-0.642	-0.501	-0.641	-0.529	-0.663	-0.514	-0.637
8 N	-0.243	-0.507	-0.243	-0.507	0.256	-0.473	0.204	-0.462	0.102	-0.471	0.268	-0.472
9 N	-0.609	-0.652	-0.609	-0.652	-0.245	-0.626	-0.320	-0.625	-0.344	-0.636	-0.526	-0.627
10 C	0.201	-0.261	0.201	-0.261	0.096	-0.272	0.103	-0.273	0.067	-0.273	0.242	-0.275
11 C	0.369	-0.128	0.369	-0.128	-0.035	-0.129	-0.019	-0.132	0.173	-0.143	-0.069	-0.122
12 C	-0.437	-0.464	-0.437	-0.464	-0.072	-0.479	-0.067	-0.477	-0.146	-0.478	-0.336	-0.473
13 C	-0.162	-0.244	-0.162	-0.244	-0.323	-0.248	-0.337	-0.246	-0.258	-0.248	-0.289	-0.246
14 C	-0.339	0.060	-0.339	0.060	-0.102	0.060	0.129	0.070	-0.059	0.063	0.060	0.062
15 C	0.486	-0.104	0.486	-0.104	0.079	-0.100	0.172	-0.104	-0.188	-0.096	0.024	-0.103
16 C	0.459	0.047	0.459	0.047	0.275	0.055	0.316	0.057	0.515	0.044	0.423	0.046
17 C	-0.139	-0.452	-0.139	-0.452	-0.212	-0.458	-0.205	-0.458	-0.185	-0.454	-0.173	-0.453
18 C	0.258	0.061	0.258	0.061	0.110	0.053	0.102	0.050	-0.095	0.037	0.136	0.055
19 C	0.443	0.715	0.443	0.715	0.368	0.682	0.423	0.675	0.495	0.691	0.678	0.677
20 C	-0.030	0.045	-0.030	0.045	0.101	0.044	0.154	0.042	0.379	0.048	0.094	0.047
21 C	-0.205	-0.082	-0.205	-0.082	-0.324	-0.091	-0.284	-0.088	-0.498	-0.076	-0.135	-0.082
22 C	-0.120	-0.205	-0.120	-0.205	-0.103	-0.217	-0.051	-0.209	-0.073	-0.214	0.007	-0.203
23 C	-0.100	-0.472	-0.100	-0.472	-0.378	-0.474	-0.374	-0.472	-0.299	-0.473	-0.176	-0.479
24 C	0.220	-0.452	0.220	-0.452	0.148	-0.456	0.137	-0.457	0.151	-0.455	0.153	-0.454
25 C	-0.331	-0.691	-0.331	-0.691	-0.329	-0.691	-0.336	-0.692	-0.307	-0.688	-0.355	-0.692
26 C	-0.343	-0.673	-0.343	-0.673	-0.314	-0.677	-0.297	-0.678	-0.342	-0.675	-0.310	-0.675
27 C	-0.338	-0.826	-0.338	-0.826	-0.255	-0.813	-0.363	-0.825	-0.145	-0.825	-0.311	-0.826
28 H	0.002	0.253	0.002	0.253	0.066	0.261	0.062	0.262	0.054	0.254	0.035	0.277
29 H	-0.025	0.219	-0.025	0.219	0.093	0.283	0.090	0.282	0.019	0.320	0.090	0.251
30 H	0.117	0.234	0.117	0.234	0.072	0.258	0.076	0.259	0.090	0.254	0.119	0.245
31 H	0.107	0.260	0.107	0.260	0.047	0.280	0.042	0.282	0.041	0.276	0.110	0.279
32 H	0.059	0.193	0.059	0.193	0.142	0.251	0.150	0.252	0.117	0.245	0.106	0.233
33 H	0.085	0.234	0.085	0.234	0.157	0.270	0.167	0.270	0.132	0.256	0.141	0.282
34 H	0.121	0.231	0.121	0.231	0.122	0.239	0.077	0.250	0.088	0.229	0.062	0.232
35 H	0.048	0.285	0.048	0.285	0.161	0.297	0.093	0.301	0.237	0.282	0.113	0.285
36 H	-0.129	0.240	-0.129	0.240	0.084	0.242	-0.059	0.217	-0.004	0.256	-0.160	0.232
37 H	0.024	0.231	0.024	0.231	0.088	0.248	0.086	0.248	0.066	0.236	0.062	0.243
38 H	0.032	0.223	0.032	0.223	0.075	0.234	0.074	0.235	0.067	0.231	0.045	0.224
39 H	0.011	0.219	0.011	0.219	0.081	0.246	0.029	0.210	0.107	0.256	0.093	0.248
40 H	0.079	0.220	0.079	0.220	0.098	0.234	0.069	0.231	0.033	0.222	0.049	0.217
41 H	0.303	0.435	0.303	0.435	0.228	0.454	0.251	0.450	0.260	0.458	0.286	0.434
42 H	0.201	0.234	0.201	0.234	0.265	0.244	0.226	0.244	0.285	0.236	0.167	0.229
43 H	0.143	0.265	0.143	0.265	0.170	0.271	0.142	0.274	0.170	0.262	0.144	0.272
44 H	0.017	0.241	0.017	0.241	0.162	0.265	0.160	0.263	0.165	0.293	0.065	0.275
45 H	0.040	0.186	0.040	0.186	0.161	0.252	0.169	0.253	0.154	0.250	0.087	0.226
46 H	0.092	0.234	0.092	0.234	0.165	0.264	0.170	0.264	0.115	0.234	0.127	0.276
47 H	-0.022	0.229	-0.022	0.229	0.000	0.235	0.004	0.236	0.001	0.233	0.001	0.237
48 H	-0.022	0.227	-0.022	0.227	0.007	0.230	0.006	0.231	0.018	0.235	-0.008	0.227
49 H	0.113	0.242	0.113	0.242	0.128	0.252	0.134	0.252	0.116	0.244	0.130	0.244
50 H	0.121	0.250	0.121	0.250	0.139	0.260	0.134	0.262	0.109	0.246	0.121	0.254
51 H	0.115	0.246	0.115	0.246	0.102	0.233	0.095	0.232	0.119	0.242	0.116	0.241
52 H	0.417	0.504	0.417	0.504	0.429	0.491	0.415	0.484	0.434	0.484	0.419	0.497

53 H	0.397	0.478	0.397	0.478	0.447	0.499	0.410	0.484	0.449	0.491	0.394	0.476
54 H	0.077	0.224	0.077	0.224	0.083	0.231	0.080	0.232	0.084	0.228	0.074	0.225
55 H	0.077	0.232	0.077	0.232	0.095	0.247	0.093	0.249	0.092	0.240	0.082	0.238
56 H	0.081	0.224	0.081	0.224	0.088	0.233	0.083	0.233	0.086	0.226	0.080	0.229
57 H	0.383	0.478	0.383	0.478	0.445	0.494	0.388	0.482	0.316	0.495	0.321	0.499
58 H	0.178	0.251	0.178	0.251	0.171	0.262	0.192	0.261	0.126	0.249	0.167	0.250
59 H	0.110	0.231	0.110	0.231	0.109	0.245	0.130	0.240	0.056	0.231	0.102	0.232
60 H	0.117	0.253	0.117	0.253	0.126	0.252	0.146	0.249	0.075	0.251	0.113	0.246
61 H		-		-	0.206	0.490	0.232	0.486	0.225	0.483	0.139	0.478
62 Cl		-		-		-		-	-0.738	-0.832	-0.688	-0.809

Table 4. Bond Orders, Expressed as Wiberg Index for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and in Aqueous Solution (PCM) by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

B3LYP/6-31G*						
Atoms	Free Base		Cationic		Hydrochloride	
	gas	PCM	gas	PCM	gas	PCM
1 Cl	1.095	1.090	1.099	1.091	1.097	1.093
2 S	2.197	2.199	2.206	2.203	2.193	2.199
3 O	1.998	1.996	1.990	1.988	2.000	1.986
4 O	1.780	1.775	1.800	1.799	1.794	1.787
5 O	1.795	1.798	1.779	1.801	1.778	1.789
6 O	1.805	1.804	1.788	1.798	1.758	1.765
7 O	1.954	1.953	2.001	1.991	1.976	1.986
8 N	3.126	3.116	3.425	3.440	3.430	3.410
9 N	3.217	3.232	3.262	3.261	3.239	3.258
10 C	3.953	3.954	3.945	3.944	3.949	3.940
11 C	3.930	3.937	3.859	3.858	3.814	3.889
12 C	3.892	3.891	3.870	3.868	3.876	3.877
13 C	3.868	3.869	3.791	3.788	3.813	3.797
14 C	3.859	3.863	3.857	3.857	3.863	3.862
15 C	3.911	3.912	3.890	3.890	3.906	3.902
16 C	3.881	3.887	3.879	3.879	3.869	3.882
17 C	3.910	3.910	3.897	3.896	3.904	3.904
18 C	3.872	3.873	3.853	3.880	3.841	3.857
19 C	3.870	3.873	3.893	3.899	3.886	3.899
20 C	3.872	3.875	3.869	3.870	3.880	3.890
21 C	3.870	3.873	3.853	3.857	3.858	3.865
22 C	3.937	3.936	3.937	3.935	3.942	3.934
23 C	3.802	3.805	3.721	3.720	3.706	3.717
24 C	3.906	3.906	3.901	3.901	3.902	3.903
25 C	3.834	3.833	3.831	3.831	3.836	3.834
26 C	3.851	3.851	3.839	3.838	3.846	3.847
27 C	3.808	3.808	3.800	3.803	3.810	3.811
28 H	0.940	0.940	0.935	0.935	0.938	0.927
29 H	0.957	0.963	0.922	0.922	0.905	0.939
30 H	0.948	0.948	0.935	0.935	0.938	0.942
31 H	0.935	0.934	0.923	0.922	0.925	0.924
32 H	0.968	0.968	0.939	0.939	0.942	0.948
33 H	0.947	0.945	0.928	0.928	0.936	0.923
34 H	0.951	0.953	0.947	0.942	0.952	0.951
35 H	0.924	0.925	0.916	0.914	0.924	0.925
36 H	0.948	0.949	0.945	0.958	0.939	0.952
37 H	0.949	0.949	0.941	0.941	0.946	0.943
38 H	0.953	0.953	0.948	0.947	0.949	0.953
39 H	0.956	0.957	0.943	0.960	0.938	0.942

40 H	0.956	0.957	0.949	0.950	0.955	0.958
41 H	0.814	0.813	0.798	0.801	0.796	0.815
42 H	0.952	0.952	0.947	0.946	0.950	0.955
43 H	0.933	0.932	0.930	0.928	0.934	0.929
44 H	0.946	0.945	0.931	0.932	0.917	0.930
45 H	0.971	0.970	0.937	0.937	0.939	0.950
46 H	0.947	0.947	0.931	0.931	0.946	0.926
47 H	0.950	0.950	0.950	0.947	0.948	0.946
48 H	0.950	0.951	0.950	0.949	0.947	0.951
49 H	0.943	0.942	0.938	0.938	0.942	0.942
50 H	0.939	0.938	0.934	0.933	0.941	0.937
51 H	0.941	0.941	0.948	0.948	0.944	0.944
52 H	0.748	0.750	0.762	0.767	0.769	0.755
53 H	0.773	0.778	0.752	0.768	0.760	0.775
54 H	0.952	0.952	0.948	0.948	0.950	0.951
55 H	0.947	0.947	0.940	0.939	0.944	0.944
56 H	0.951	0.951	0.947	0.947	0.951	0.949
57 H	0.773	0.773	0.757	0.769	0.760	0.754
58 H	0.938	0.937	0.932	0.933	0.939	0.939
59 H	0.950	0.950	0.943	0.945	0.950	0.949
60 H	0.940	0.941	0.940	0.941	0.941	0.943
61 H	-	-	0.766	0.770	0.773	0.782
62 Cl	-	-	-	-	0.325	0.367

Table 5. Molecular Electrostatic Potentials for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and in Aqueous Solution (PCM) by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

B3LYP/6-31G*						
Atoms	Free Base		Cationic		Hydrochloride	
	gas	PCM	gas	PCM	gas	PCM
1 Cl	-64.393	-64.399	-64.307	-64.313	-64.400	-64.380
2 S	-59.203	-59.214	-59.108	-59.122	-59.210	-59.209
3 O	-22.308	-22.322	-22.203	-22.211	-22.311	-22.310
4 O	-22.335	-22.358	-22.224	-22.218	-22.328	-22.340
5 O	-22.306	-22.315	-22.202	-22.219	-22.299	-22.323
6 O	-22.302	-22.315	-22.214	-22.213	-22.342	-22.348
7 O	-22.342	-22.369	-22.202	-22.204	-22.312	-22.310
8 N	-18.357	-18.365	-18.097	-18.085	-18.213	-18.212
9 N	-18.312	-18.312	-18.187	-18.186	-18.303	-18.276
10 C	-14.741	-14.745	-14.590	-14.586	-14.688	-14.693
11 C	-14.702	-14.705	-14.532	-14.528	-14.665	-14.633
12 C	-14.743	-14.747	-14.590	-14.587	-14.699	-14.693
13 C	-14.722	-14.725	-14.548	-14.542	-14.649	-14.657
14 C	-14.688	-14.695	-14.582	-14.582	-14.682	-14.684
15 C	-14.683	-14.686	-14.579	-14.581	-14.679	-14.665
16 C	-14.697	-14.712	-14.593	-14.588	-14.699	-14.705
17 C	-14.745	-14.746	-14.624	-14.621	-14.709	-14.711
18 C	-14.683	-14.684	-14.587	-14.590	-14.694	-14.702
19 C	-14.636	-14.644	-14.494	-14.493	-14.609	-14.593
20 C	-14.677	-14.676	-14.585	-14.588	-14.695	-14.700
21 C	-14.661	-14.670	-14.568	-14.574	-14.673	-14.673
22 C	-14.664	-14.660	-14.577	-14.579	-14.669	-14.649
23 C	-14.728	-14.734	-14.544	-14.536	-14.674	-14.665
24 C	-14.744	-14.747	-14.641	-14.639	-14.719	-14.719
25 C	-14.731	-14.728	-14.647	-14.648	-14.735	-14.716

26 C	-14.751	-14.754	-14.664	-14.662	-14.732	-14.732
27 C	-14.724	-14.726	-14.634	-14.648	-14.728	-14.726
28 H	-1.139	-1.151	-0.988	-0.984	-1.085	-1.093
29 H	-1.115	-1.101	-0.937	-0.932	-1.071	-1.043
30 H	-1.125	-1.117	-0.978	-0.975	-1.087	-1.077
31 H	-1.128	-1.137	-0.974	-0.971	-1.082	-1.081
32 H	-1.133	-1.128	-0.954	-0.947	-1.055	-1.058
33 H	-1.128	-1.129	-0.951	-0.944	-1.051	-1.062
34 H	-1.118	-1.116	-1.014	-1.019	-1.117	-1.115
35 H	-1.094	-1.093	-0.995	-0.996	-1.094	-1.076
36 H	-1.128	-1.140	-1.022	-1.020	-1.132	-1.134
37 H	-1.133	-1.132	-1.014	-1.011	-1.098	-1.100
38 H	-1.133	-1.129	-1.013	-1.010	-1.098	-1.099
39 H	-1.112	-1.099	-1.021	-1.019	-1.126	-1.138
40 H	-1.109	-1.090	-1.017	-1.019	-1.132	-1.136
41 H	-1.010	-1.001	-0.888	-0.888	-1.006	-0.975
42 H	-1.107	-1.099	-1.012	-1.019	-1.118	-1.116
43 H	-1.091	-1.077	-1.003	-1.005	-1.095	-1.076
44 H	-1.131	-1.145	-0.945	-0.937	-1.079	-1.066
45 H	-1.133	-1.129	-0.945	-0.936	-1.073	-1.058
46 H	-1.127	-1.134	-0.945	-0.937	-1.067	-1.065
47 H	-1.137	-1.141	-1.034	-1.032	-1.112	-1.112
48 H	-1.137	-1.138	-1.033	-1.032	-1.112	-1.111
49 H	-1.104	-1.095	-1.022	-1.024	-1.110	-1.090
50 H	-1.110	-1.105	-1.027	-1.028	-1.113	-1.095
51 H	-1.111	-1.109	-1.025	-1.025	-1.115	-1.094
52 H	-1.018	-1.029	-0.908	-0.898	-1.011	-1.023
53 H	-0.985	-0.958	-0.885	-0.900	-0.981	-1.003
54 H	-1.132	-1.131	-1.045	-1.043	-1.113	-1.113
55 H	-1.132	-1.133	-1.045	-1.044	-1.114	-1.113
56 H	-1.132	-1.133	-1.045	-1.044	-1.113	-1.113
57 H	-0.982	-0.959	-0.896	-0.895	-1.028	-1.031
58 H	-1.106	-1.102	-1.019	-1.032	-1.111	-1.108
59 H	-1.114	-1.104	-1.027	-1.040	-1.119	-1.116
60 H	-1.117	-1.123	-1.027	-1.041	-1.123	-1.119
61 H	-	-	-0.840	-0.832	-0.956	-0.964
62 Cl	-	-	-	-	-64.522	-64.512

Examining both charges for all species from Table 3 and Figure 4, we can see that the NPA charges on the S and H atoms have high values (more positive) than the MK charges while, on O and Cl the behaviours are opposite. In both media, the MK charges show the highest differences between the species while the NPA charges are practically similar. In the three species, the most negative NPA and MK charges on N9 and C21 are observed while H52, H57 and H61 show most positive values because they are forming possible H bonds.

In the three species, on O4 and O5 show most negative MK and NPA charges are observed while in solution on the O6 atoms of hydrochloride form are observed the most

negative NPA values. Different behaviours of MK and NPA charges are observed on N8 because the three forms proposed in both phases show negative values however, the MK charges on N8 of hydrochloride and cationic forms show positive values in both media, as expected because both species are charged. On C15 atoms the MK charges, same similarities are observed from Figure 4.

Analysing the BOs, shown as Wiberg indexes, from Table 4, similar values are observed for all atoms in both phases; with exception of O6, C11 and C13 atoms corresponding to the free base which show higher bond orders in both media, as given in Figure 5.

However, for the nitrogen atoms the bond orders are lower in the free base than in the other ones, presenting a greater difference for the N8, in both phases; while O7 atom, belonging to carbonyl group, show clearly double bond

character for cationic and hydrochloride species. In addition, the C23 atom attached to the N of the pyrrole ring has a higher bond order for the free base because for the other two species those sites are protonated.

Figure 4. NPA and MK Charges for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas (upper) and in Aqueous Solution (bottom) by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Figure 5. Bond Orders for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas and in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

MEP values for the three clindamycin's species were calculated with the MK charges (Besler, Merz Jr., & Kollman, 1990) (Table 5). Obviously, the chlorine atoms show the most negative values due to its electronegativity and the less negative values are observed on H53 and H57 of hydroxyl groups. Evaluating the MEP values on O, the most negative values are shown on O7 and O6 of FB and HCl in both phases. On O4 of CA in the gas phase is observed the most negative value while in aqueous solution on O5. Considering the MEP values for nitrogen atoms, the most negative value on N8 of FB is observed

while in CA and HCl the most negative values are observed on N9, as estimated because the N8 are protonated in these two species. Evaluating, the mapped MEP surfaces from Figure 6, the nucleophilic sites (red colour) are clearly located on O while the electrophilic ones (blue colour) are located on H belonging to OH groups. This analysis shows similar colorations on MEP values surfaces for FB and HCl forms in both media but the higher variation is observed in HCl due to additional Cl where identified clear sites of H bonds formation.

Figure 6. Calculated Electrostatic Potential Surfaces on the Molecular Surfaces of Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase. B3LYP Functional and 6-31G* Basis Set. Isodensity Value of 0.005

NBO and AIM Calculations

Stabilities of proposed forms of clindamycin in two media were studied using NBO and AIM calculations (Glendening, et al., 1996; Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001; Bader, 1990). The calculated energies $E^{(2)}$ (donor $\rightarrow$ acceptor) at B3LYP/631G* theory level are shown in Table 6. All forms in both phases have four similar delocalizations of type $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$. On the other hand, the charge transfers

from the lone pairs of O7 to antibonding orbitals N8-H61 of pyrrole ring can be observed for CA and HCl species in the gas phase while in solution it is only observed for CA. Also, HCl in both phases, presents a new charge delocalization from the lone pairs of additional Cl (Cl62) to antibonding orbital O6-H57 while in solution another transfer from the lone pairs of Cl62 atom to antibonding orbital N8-H61 bond is also observed.

Table 6. Main Delocalization Energy (in kJ/mol) for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Delocalization	GAS			PCM		
	Free Base	Cation	Hydrochloride	Free Base	Cation	Hydrochloride
$LP(2)S2 \rightarrow \sigma^*(O3-C21)$	40.379	43.221	39.208	41.591	43.347	41.716
$LP(2)O4 \rightarrow \sigma^*(C14-C16)$	42.636	--	35.237	40.504	--	40.212
$LP(2)O5 \rightarrow \sigma^*(C18-C20)$	34.025	33.273	30.807	30.347	28.048	31.475
$LP(2)O7 \rightarrow \sigma^*(N8-H61)$	--	68.385	66.796	--	36.617	--
$LP(2)O7 \rightarrow \sigma^*(N9-C19)$	88.950	90.915	89.703	81.632	91.500	87.069
$LP(2)O7 \rightarrow \sigma^*(C11-C19)$	84.561	75.073	69.681	80.883	79.211	90.037
$LP(3)Cl62 \rightarrow \sigma^*(O6-H57)$	--	--	123.394	--	--	74.320
$LP(4)Cl62 \rightarrow \sigma^*(N8-H61)$	--	--	--	--	--	106.715
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \sigma^*}$	290.551	144.879	352.793	273.957	278.723	471.544
$LP(1)N9 \rightarrow \pi^*(O7-C19)$	269.986	374.862	340.336	285.619	361.194	310.281
$\Delta E_{LP \rightarrow \pi^*}$	269.986	374.862	340.336	285.619	361.194	310.281
ΔE_{Total}	560.537	519.741	693.129	560.576	639.917	781.825

When all energies are compared, clearly the HCl form is favoured by higher total energy and, hence, it form has the highest stability in both media.

Here, intra and intermolecular interactions of the three species in both phases were studied employing the Bader's theory with the AIM program (Biegler-König, Schönbohm, & Bayles, 2001; Bader, 1990). Hence, the electron density, the Laplacian values, and, the eigenvalues of the Hessian matrix and the λ_1/λ_3 ratio were computed in the Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs). In the Table 7, Table 8, Table 9 and Table 10 the analysis of BCPs and RCPs are presented for the three

species of clindamycin in both phases at the same level of theory. The results show modifications between the properties of the pyrrole (RCP1) and pyrane (RCP2) rings, resulting higher for the pyrrole rings. For free base can be observed that the electronic density values of both rings decrease in aqueous phase with respect to gas phase, while for cationic form $\rho(r)$ increases slightly in both rings. However, for hydrochloride the density of pyrrole ring decreases while that of pyrane ring increases. Comparing the $\nabla^2 \rho(r)$ in aqueous solution with respect to gas phase, these values are higher for both rings of cationic form. In the free base, the value of $\nabla^2 \rho(r)$ of pyrrole ring increases while the

corresponding to pyrane ring decreases. In the hydrochloride specie the behaviour of $\nabla^2\rho(r)$ is

inverse, thus, the value of pyrrole ring decreases while increases for pyrane ring.

Table 7. Analysis of Bond Critical Points (BCP) and Ring Critical Points (RCP) for Cationic form of Clindamycin in Both Phases by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Cationic														
Gas														
Parameters (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11--H60	RCPN1	C11--O3	RCPN2	O3--H41	RCPN3	O7--H61	RCPN4	O7--H51	RCPN5	O5--H52	RCPN6
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0363	0.0186	0.0028	0.0022	0.0083	0.0080	0.0227	0.0202	0.0447	0.0304	0.0057	0.0055	0.0190	0.0188
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.2524	0.1213	0.0092	0.0088	0.0308	0.0344	0.0928	0.1256	0.1446	0.2004	0.0225	0.0236	0.0770	0.0916
λ_1	-0.0383	-0.0144	-0.0020	-0.0015	-0.0056	-0.0046	-0.0259	-0.0177	-0.0678	-0.0344	-0.0026	-0.0016	-0.0206	-0.0184
λ_2	0.1417	0.0661	-0.0019	0.0036	-0.0039	0.0057	-0.0194	0.0270	-0.0625	0.0716	-0.0019	0.0025	-0.0084	0.0102
λ_3	0.1491	0.0697	0.0131	0.0068	0.0404	0.0332	0.1380	0.1161	0.2750	0.1634	0.0270	0.0229	0.1061	0.0998
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2569	0.2066	0.1527	0.2206	0.1386	0.1385	0.1877	0.1524	0.2465	0.2105	0.0963	0.0699	0.1941	0.1844
Distance (Å)			3.283		3.242		2.063		1.770		2.860		2.172	
PCM														
Parameters (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11--H60	RCPN1	C11--O3	RCPN2	O3--N9	RCPN3	O7--H61	RCPN4				
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0365	0.0187	0.0031	0.0023	0.0079	0.0077	0.0162	0.0162	0.0328	0.0262				
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.2544	0.1232	0.0104	0.0092	0.0296	0.0324	0.0760	0.0828	0.1072	0.1632				
λ_1	-0.0387	-0.0143	-0.0023	-0.0016	-0.0054	-0.0046	-0.0151	-0.0141	-0.0437	-0.0281				
λ_2	0.1426	0.0666	-0.0022	0.0041	-0.0036	0.0051	-0.0034	0.0038	-0.0375	0.0496				
λ_3	0.1425	0.0707	0.0147	0.0068	0.0385	0.0320	0.0947	0.0933	0.1885	0.1416				
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2716	0.2023	0.1565	0.2353	0.1403	0.1437	0.1594	0.1511	0.2318	0.1984				
Distance (Å)			3.179		3.252		2.698		1.935					

Note: #The quantities are in atomic units and distances in Å.

Table 8. Analysis of Bond Critical Points (BCP) and Ring Critical Points (RCP) for Free Base of Clindamycin by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

B3LYP/6-31G*																
Gas																
Parámetros (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11-H60	RCPN1	C11-O3	RCPN2	O3-H44	O6-H44	RCPN3	RCPN4	N9-H44	RCPN5	RCPN6	O7-H52	RCPN7	RCPN8
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0379	0.0190	0.0041	0.0029	0.0083	0.0079	0.0032	0.0034	0.0021	0.0020	0.0058	0.0030	0.0058	0.0276	0.0076	0.0092
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.2696	0.1244	0.0136	0.0116	0.0312	0.0340	0.0133	0.0146	0.0104	0.0080	0.0215	0.0124	0.0216	0.0860	0.0336	0.0412
λ_1	-0.0391	-0.0142	-0.0032	-0.0021	-0.0059	-0.0049	-0.0027	-0.0027	-0.0010	-0.0009	-0.0031	-0.0020	-0.0030	-0.0377	-0.0027	-0.0061
λ_2	0.1489	0.0688	-0.0030	0.0055	-0.0045	0.0069	-0.0021	-0.0019	0.0044	0.0022	-0.0006	0.0031	0.0006	-0.0368	0.0017	0.0143
λ_3	0.1599	0.0699	0.0197	0.0083	0.0415	0.0322	0.0180	0.0192	0.0071	0.0066	0.0252	0.0113	0.0241	0.1605	0.0347	0.0332
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2445	0.2031	0.1624	0.2530	0.1422	0.1522	0.1500	0.1406	0.1408	0.1364	0.1230	0.1770	0.0249	0.2349	0.0778	0.1837
Distancias (Å)			3.115		3.220		2.990	3.004			2.904			1.931		
PCM																
Parámetros (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11-H60	RCPN1	C11-O3	RCPN2	O6-H44	RCPN3	RCPN4	O7-H52	RCPN5	RCPN6				
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0377	0.0189	0.0026	0.0020	0.0079	0.0076	0.0027	0.0015	0.0018	0.0297	0.0093	0.0076				
$\nabla^2\rho(r_c)$	0.2672	0.1240	0.0084	0.0080	0.0296	0.0324	0.0120	0.0080	0.0072	0.0920	0.0416	0.0340				
λ_1	-0.0389	-0.0140	-0.0019	-0.0014	-0.0055	-0.0047	-0.0021	-0.0003	-0.0011	-0.0414	-0.0060	-0.0025				
λ_2	0.1470	0.0683	-0.0017	0.0034	-0.0039	0.0059	-0.0019	-0.0025	0.0023	-0.0408	0.0129	0.0024				
λ_3	0.1590	0.0697	0.0119	0.0061	0.0392	0.0312	0.0161	0.0056	0.0061	0.1743	0.0345	0.0340				
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2446	0.2009	0.1597	0.2295	0.1403	0.1506	0.1304	0.0536	0.1803	0.2375	0.1739	0.0735				
Distancias (Å)			3.253		3.258		3.074			1.893						

Note: #The quantities are in atomic units and distances in Å.

Table 9. Analysis of Bond Critical Points (BCP) and Ring Critical Points (RCP) for Hydrochloride of Clindamycin in Gas Phase by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

B3LYP/6-31G*														
GAS														
Parámetros (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11-H60	C11-O3	RCPN1	RCPN2	O3-H41	RCPN3	O6-H41	RCPN4	O7-H51	RCPN5	O7-H61	RCPN6
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0365	0.0182	0.0027	0.0096	0.0025	0.0086	0.0209	0.0200	0.0119	0.0099	0.0065	0.0055	0.0441	0.0302
$\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$	0.2536	0.1880	0.0090	0.0360	0.0096	0.0396	0.0860	0.1140	0.0416	0.0396	0.0248	0.0240	0.1428	0.1988
λ_1	-0.0386	-0.0143	-0.0019	-0.0067	-0.0017	-0.0050	-0.0230	-0.0176	-0.0121	-0.0087	-0.0048	-0.0008	-0.0665	-0.0344
λ_2	0.1424	0.0642	-0.0016	-0.0062	0.0029	0.0103	-0.0147	0.0199	-0.0115	0.0169	-0.0036	0.0063	-0.0614	0.0701
λ_3	0.1499	0.0680	0.0126	0.0488	0.0086	0.0342	0.1236	0.1117	0.0651	0.0316	0.0332	0.0183	0.2709	0.1631
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2575	0.2103	0.1508	0.1373	0.1977	0.1462	0.1861	0.1576	0.1859	0.2753	0.1446	0.0437	0.2455	0.2109
Distancias (Å)			3.317	3.133			2.133		2.370		2.749		1.777	
GAS														
Parámetros (a.u.)	O5-H52	RCPN7	C162-H29	C162-H44	RCPN8	C162-H57	RCPN9	RCPN10	C162-H36	RCPN11	C162-H39	RCPN12	RCPN13	
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0228	0.0211	0.0202	0.0131	0.0077	0.0346	0.0031	0.0025	0.0063	0.0051	0.0064	0.0050	0.0061	
$\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$	0.0832	0.1156	0.0552	0.0436	0.0304	0.0848	0.0140	0.0009	0.0200	0.0192	0.0200	0.0172	0.0216	
λ_1	-0.0275	-0.0207	-0.0204	-0.0116	-0.0048	-0.0439	-0.0016	-0.0009	-0.0044	-0.0015	-0.0041	-0.0011	-0.0035	
λ_2	-0.0197	0.0279	-0.0199	-0.0103	0.0115	-0.0437	0.0034	0.0038	-0.0038	0.0061	-0.0028	0.0045	0.0043	
λ_3	0.1306	0.1085	0.0963	0.0654	0.0236	0.1726	0.0122	0.0059	0.0275	0.0148	0.0269	0.0137	0.0209	
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2106	0.1908	0.2118	0.1774	0.2034	0.2543	0.1311	0.1525	0.1600	0.1013	0.1524	0.0803	0.1675	
Distancias (Å)	2.074		2.388	2.605		2.071			3.019		3.041			

Note: #The quantities are in atomic units and distances in Å.

Table 10. Analysis of Bond Critical Points (BCP) and Ring Critical Points (RCP) for Hydrochloride of Clindamycin in Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

PCM												
Parámetros (a.u.)	RCP1	RCP2	C11-H60	RCPN1	C11-O3	RCPN2	RCPN3	O3-H44	O6-H44	RCPN4	O7-H36	RCPN5
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0364	0.0189	0.0031	0.0023	0.0078	0.0076	0.0023	0.0025	0.0039	0.0021	0.0100	0.0088
$\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$	0.2524	0.1244	0.0100	0.0092	0.0295	0.0320	0.0100	0.0108	0.0164	0.0100	0.0408	0.0388
λ_1	-0.0381	-0.0138	-0.0023	-0.0016	-0.0054	-0.0047	-0.0015	-0.0019	-0.0034	-0.0013	-0.0069	-0.0043
λ_2	0.1408	0.0674	-0.0021	0.0041	-0.0039	0.0058	0.0023	-0.0014	-0.0031	0.0032	-0.0023	0.0030
λ_3	0.1498	0.0707	0.0144	0.0067	0.0389	0.0311	0.0093	0.0140	0.0226	0.0081	0.0500	0.0400
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.2543	0.1952	0.1597	0.2388	0.1388	0.1511	0.1613	0.1357	0.1504	0.1605	0.1380	0.1075
Distancias (Å)			3.258		3.254			3.078	2.904		2.576	
PCM												
Parámetros (a.u.)	RCPN6	O7-H52	RCPN7	C162-H36	RCPN8	C162-H57	RCPN9	C162-H61	RCPN10			
$\rho(r_c)$	0.0085	0.0241	0.0099	0.0084	0.0065	0.0242	0.0024	0.0302	0.0033			
$\nabla^2 \rho(r_c)$	0.0376	0.0784	0.0428	0.0256	0.0240	0.0660	0.0096	0.0660	0.0108			
λ_1	-0.0047	-0.0315	-0.0070	-0.0062	-0.0041	-0.0280	-0.0010	-0.0354	-0.0009			
λ_2	0.0141	-0.0311	0.0035	-0.0054	0.0072	-0.0277	0.0035	-0.0347	0.0051			
λ_3	0.0282	0.1409	0.0462	0.0371	0.0211	0.1219	0.0073	0.1361	0.0068			
$ \lambda_1 /\lambda_3$	0.1667	0.2236	0.1515	0.1671	0.1943	0.2297	0.1370	0.2601	0.1323			
Distancias (Å)		1.989		2.874		2.240		2.181				

Note: #The quantities are in atomic units and distances in Å.

When the values of $\rho(r)$ are low, the relationship $|\lambda_1|/\lambda_3 < 1$ and $\nabla^2\rho(r)$ show positive values indicate that the interaction is ionic or highly polar covalent. Additionally, in the molecular graphics for these species presented in Figure 7 can see only the new BCPs for the three species of clindamycin in both phases. Here, for cation and hydrochloride species, in gas phase, we can

clearly see the $nO7 \rightarrow \sigma^*(N8-H61)$ interaction predicted by NBO calculations with the expected hydrogen bond formation, due to the interatomic distances between $N8-H61 \cdots O7$ which are 1.770 and 1.777 respectively. In solution, that transition is only observed for the cationic form.

Figure 7. Molecular Graphics for the Three Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution Showing All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) at B3LYP/6-31G* Level of Theory

We can see that topological properties (Table 7 and 9) are higher in that hydrogen bond due to the lower distance. The calculations predict for the hydrochloride in both phases other transitions, as the $nCl62 \rightarrow \sigma^*(O6-H57)$ transition while, only in aqueous solution, the $nCl62 \rightarrow \sigma^*(N8-H61)$ interaction. These halogen bonds formed are observed in the AIM molecular graphs and their distances in Tables 7, 8, 9 and 10. However, in Figure 7, we can see other new bonds critical points and that due to the greater interatomic distances that they

present by NBO calculations these were not predicted. Therefore, to help better interpreting figure, critical points involved in hydrogen bonds are in red circle while critical points involved in halogen bonds in blue circle. Thus, is possible to distinguish the different new BCPs that present each of three species in both media. Hence, the HCl species is the most stable because this species presents the highest number of BCPs, in concordance with those predicted by NBO analysis. In Figures 8 to 10 the AIM molecular graphs are presented in full detail for the three species of clindamycin in both phases.

Figure 8. Molecular Graphics for Free Base of Clindamycin in Gas Phase (upper) and Aqueous Solution (bottom) Showing the Geometry of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) at the B3LYP/6-31G* Level

Gas phase

Aqueous solution

Figure 9. Molecular Graphics for Cationic form of Clindamycin in Gas Phase (upper) and Aqueous Solution (bottom) Showing the Geometry of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) at the B3LYP/6-31G* Level

Figure 10. Molecular Graphics for Hydrochloride of Clindamycin in Gas Phase (upper) and Aqueous Solution (bottom) Showing the Geometry of All Their Bond Critical Points (BCPs) and Ring Critical Points (RCPs) at the B3LYP/6-31G* Level

HOMO-LUMO Gap and Descriptors of Reactivity

Gap values, suggested by Parr and Pearson (Parr, & Pearson, 1983; Parr, & Yang, 1989; Parr, Szentpály, & Liu, 1999; Kiyooka, Kaneno, & Fujiyama, 2013) as the difference between the frontier orbitals, and some descriptors are remarkable factors to predict reactivities and behaviors of many species. Here, these parameters for all forms of clindamycin in both phases were predicted using the B3LYP/6-31G* method. Thus, when the gap values are very close the species is reactive (Rudyk, Checa, Catalán, & Brandán, 2019; Romano, Davies, &

Brandán, 2017; Vakili, et al., 2021; Darugar, et al., 2022). In this work, the chemical potential, electronegativity, global hardness, softness electrophilicity index and nucleophilicity index descriptors are calculated from the gap values using known equations (Rudyk, Checa, Catalán, & Brandán, 2019; Romano, Davies, & Brandán, 2017; Vakili, et al., 2021; Darugar, et al., 2022). These parameters for the three forms of clindamycin in the two phases are given in Table 11 together with the descriptors. The results show that in both phases, the hydrochloride form is the most reactive species of clindamycin; the cationic form has a slight lower reactivity while the free base is markedly least reactive.

Table 11. Frontier Molecular HOMO and LUMO Orbitals and Some Descriptors for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Gas Phase and Aqueous Solution by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Frontier orbitals (eV)	Metronidazole					
	Free Base		Cation		Hydrochloride	
	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM	Gas	PCM
HOMO	-5.6600	-5.6600	-8.6233	-8.2069	-5.4395	-5.5974
LUMO	0.3537	0.3537	-3.2572	-3.3443	-0.1850	-0.9932
GAP	6.0137	6.0137	5.3661	4.8627	5.2545	4.6042
Descriptors (eV)						
χ	2.6531	2.6531	5.9402	5.7756	2.8123	3.2953
μ	-2.6531	-2.6531	-5.9402	-5.7756	-2.8123	-3.2953
η	3.0068	3.0068	2.6830	2.4313	2.6273	2.3021
δ	0.1663	0.1663	0.1864	0.2056	0.1903	0.2172
ω	1.1705	1.1705	6.5758	6.8599	1.5052	2.3585
E	-0.8824	-0.8824	-2.2140	-2.3755	-1.0704	-1.4314

Vibrational study

The optimized structures of all forms of clindamycin in both phases by using the B3LYP/6-31G* method present C_1 symmetries. According to number of atoms, for FB are expected 174 normal vibration mode while for CA and HCl 177 and 180 modes, respectively; where all modes present activity in the IR and Raman spectra. The experimental infrared

spectra for hydrochloride species of clindamycin is compared in Figure 11 with the corresponding predicted for all forms in gas phase (Infrared Reference Spectra, n.d.); while the experimental Raman spectrum (SpectraBase, n.d.) and the corresponding theoretical are compared in Figure 12. Very good correlations can be observed for the proposed three forms of clindamycin.

Figure 11. Experimental Infrared Spectra of Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Solid Phase (Infrared Reference Spectra, n.d.) Compared with the Predicted for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Figure 12. Experimental Raman Spectra of Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Solid Phase (SpectraBase, n.d.) Compared with the Predicted for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species by Using the Hybrid B3LYP/6-31G* Method

At high wavenumbers, the hydrochloride form has best correlation, while at low wavenumbers, the intensities of IR bands in experimental would be justified by the presence of CA and FB species. The intense and wide IR bands in the experimental spectrum between 4000 and 3000 cm^{-1} visibly indicate the formation of H bonds, evidenced in the NBO calculations and AIM

studies, previously discussed. Table 12 shows the calculated and experimental wavenumbers, the SQM based on the 6-31G* basis set and the assignment for FB, CA and HCl species of clindamycin in gas phase. Then, discussions of assignments are presented for the most relevant groups.

Table 12. Observed and Calculated Wavenumbers (cm^{-1}) and Assignment for the Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Forms of Clindamycin in Gas Phase

IR ^c Exp.	Raman ^d Exp.	Free base ^a			Cation ^a			Hydrochloride ^a		
		Calc.	SQM ^b	Assignment	Calc	SQM ^b	Assignment	Calc	SQM ^b	Assignment
3748 w		3757	3601	ν O5-H53	3764	3608	ν O5-H53	3773	3617	ν O5-H53
3748 w		3744	3590	ν O6-H57	3746	3591	ν O6-H57			

					3683	3530	vO4-H52	3670	3518	vO4-H52
3386 s,br		3606	3457	vN9-H41	3544	3398	vN9-H41	3455	3312	vO6-H57
3282 s,br		3581	3433	vO4-H52				3251	3116	vN9-H41
3067 m					3190	3058	v _a CH ₃ (C23)	3190	3058	v _a CH ₃ (C23)
					3187	3056	v _a CH ₃ (C23)	3179	3048	v _a CH ₃ (C23)
					3173	3041	v _a CH ₃ (C27)			
3031 m	3057 vw	3166	3035	v _a CH ₃ (C27)	3163	3033	v _a CH ₃ (C27)	3163	3033	v _a CH ₃ (C27)
		3155	3025	v _a CH ₃ (C25)	3159	3029	v _a CH ₂ (C13)	3160	3029	v _a CH ₃ (C25)
					3159	3028	v _a CH ₃ (C25)			
								3149	3019	v _a CH ₂ (C13)
		3145	3015	v _a CH ₃ (C27)	3143	3014	v _a CH ₂ (C12)	3144	3014	v _a CH ₂ (C12)
		3140	3010	v _a CH ₂ (C12)	3142	3012	v _a CH ₃ (C25)	3143	3013	v _a CH ₃ (C27)
		3138	3009	v _a CH ₃ (C23)				3136	3006	v _a CH ₃ (C25)
	2999 sh	3132	3003	v _a CH ₃ (C25)	3131	3002	v _a CH ₃ (C26)			
2990m		3118	2990	vC22-H43	3122	2993	vC11-H29	3126	2997	vC16-H36
								3122	2993	v _a CH ₃ (C26)
	2989 w	3111	2983	v _a CH ₃ (C26)	3118	2989	v _a CH ₃ (C26)	3111	2983	v _a CH ₃ (C26)
					3114	2985	vC22-H43	3104	2976	vC22-H43
		3105	2977	v _a CH ₃ (C26)						
2968 m	2971sh	3098	2970	v _a CH ₃ (C23)	3099	2971	vC15-H35			
		3096	2968	vC15-H35	3097	2969	vC16-H36			
2968 m					3096	2968	v _s CH ₃ (C23)			
2958m	2960 w				3091	2964	v _s CH ₂ (C13)	3091	2963	v _s CH ₂ (C13)
					3080	2953	v _a CH ₂ (C17)	3082	2954	v _s CH ₃ (C23)
								3078	2951	vC18-H39
					3075	2947	v _s CH ₃ (C27)	3077	2950	v _a CH ₂ (C24)
		2946	2946	v _a CH ₂ (C13)	3073	2946	v _s CH ₂ (C12)	3076	2949	vC15-H35
		2940	2940	v _a CH ₂ (C24)	3069	2942	v _s CH ₃ (C25)	3068	2941	v _s CH ₂ (C12)
					3066	2939	vC18-H39	3065	2938	v _s CH ₃ (C25)
	2936 sh	3062	2936	v _s CH ₃ (C27)				3062	2936	v N8-H61
		3061	2935	vC16-H36				3061	2935	vC21-H42
		3060	2933	v _s CH ₂ (C12)				3059	2933	v _s CH ₃ (C27)
		3059	2932	v _s CH ₃ (C25)	3057	2931	v _a CH ₂ (C24)			
2924 m	2925 w				3053	2926	v _s CH ₃ (C26)	3051	2925	v _a CH ₂ (C17)
2922m		3049	2923	vC10-H28	3050	2924	vC21-H42			
		3041	2915	v _s CH ₃ (C26)	3043	2917	vC10-H28	3046	2920	v _s CH ₃ (C26)
		3036	2911	v _a CH ₂ (C17)	3038	2912	vC14-H34	3039	2913	v _s CH ₂ (C24)
2907m		3032	2907	vC21-H42	3034	2909	v _s CH ₂ (C24)	3033	2908	vC10-H28
		3031	2906	v _s CH ₂ (C24)						
					3027	2902	vC20-H40	3022	2897	vC14-H34
					3025	2900	v N8-H61			
	2893 w	3019	2894	vC14-H34	3024	2898	v _s CH ₂ (C17)	3017	2893	v _s CH ₂ (C17)
		3010	2885	v _s CH ₂ (C17)						

2865 sh		3002	2878	vC18-H39				2994	2870	vC20-H40
2860 m		2990	2867	vC20-H40				2988	2865	vC11-H29
		2951	2829	vC11-H29						
2764 sh		2935	2814	v _s CH ₃ (C23)						
2688 w		2909	2789	v _s CH ₂ (C13)						
1686 s	1698 vw	1740	1679	vC19=O7	1767	1705	vC19=O7	1750	1689	vC19=O7
1555 s		1555	1510	βN9-H41	1578	1532	βN9-H41	1591	1545	βN9-H41
1521 sh					1541	1497	δ N8-H61-C23	1540	1491	δ N8-H61-C23
1505 sh		1549	1481	δCH ₂ (C13)						
		1540	1472	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)	1540	1473	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)	1536	1473	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)
		1531	1467	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)	1535	1468	δCH ₂ (C13)	1532	1467	δCH ₂ (C13)
1466sh	1469 m	1530	1464	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)	1529	1464	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)	1530	1465	δ _a CH ₃ (C26)
	1458 m	1524	1458	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)	1525	1460	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)	1525	1460	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)
		1523	1457	δCH ₂ (C24)	1523	1457	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)	1524	1457	δCH ₂ (C24)
		1521	1455	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)				1521	1455	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)
					1521	1456	δCH ₂ (C12)	1519	1454	δCH ₂ (C12)
		1519	1454	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)	1519	1455	δCH ₂ (C24)			
1452 s		1516	1452	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)	1514	1449	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)	1515	1450	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)
	1445 m	1514	1446	δCH ₂ (C12)	1513	1447	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)			
		1510	1443	δCH ₂ (C17)	1509	1446	δCH ₂ (C17)	1514	1447	δCH ₂ (C17)
					1507	1443	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)	1509	1445	δ _a CH ₃ (C25)
		1498	1437	ρC16-H36						
								1497	1435	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)
		1495	1433	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)	1498	1432	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)	1493	1432	δ _a CH ₃ (C27)
					1479	1422	ρ N8-H61	1488	1431	ρ N8-H61
1425 m	1426 w	1488	1424	δ _s CH ₃ (C23)				1483	1424	δ(O6H57)
		1447	1404	ρC18-H39	1455	1408	ρC18-H39	1467	1414	ρC18-H39
								1456	1412	δ _s CH ₃ (C23)
		1443	1401	wagCH ₂ (C17)				1445	1400	wagCH ₂ (C17)
		1442	1396	ρ'C16-H36	1447	1399	ρ'C16-H36			
		1440	1387	wagCH ₂ (C13)	1447	1397	wagCH ₂ (C17)			
					1442	1395	δ _s CH ₃ (C23)			
	1384 m	1428	1384	ρC21-H42	1440	1392	ρC20-H40	1444	1395	ρC16-H36
								1442	1394	ρ'C16-H36
		1419	1383	ρ'C14-H34	1435	1386	wagCH ₂ (C13) ρC10-H28	1430	1388	wagCH ₂ (C13)
					1421	1383	δ _s CH ₃ (C25)	1424	1381	δ _s CH ₃ (C25)
1376 m		1418	1377	δ _s CH ₃ (C26)	1417	1381	δ _s CH ₃ (C26)	1414	1380	δ _s CH ₃ (C26)
		1412	1375	δ _s CH ₃ (C25)						
	1365 w	1408	1370	ρ'C11-H29				1405	1368	ρ'C15-H35
					1411	1374	ρC16-H36	1399	1364	ρC21-H42
					1401	1363	ρC15-H35	1392	1357	ρC11-H29
	1352 m	1393	1356	ρ'C15-H35	1395	1357	ρC21-H42			
					1390	1356	ρ'C10-H28	1386	1352	ρ'C10-H28

		1386	1345	ρ'C10-H28	1388	1347	ρ'C20-H40			
1346 sh	1341 m				1382	1345	ρ'C22-H43			
		1379	1342	ρC10-H28				1383	1343	ρC10-H28
		1376	1340	wagCH ₂ (C24)	1379	1339	wagCH ₂ (C24)	1379	1340	wagCH ₂ (C24)
		1374	1331	ρC20-H40						
1329 sh	1329 m	1367	1326	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)	1364	1326	δ _s CH ₃ (C27)	1367	1327	δ _a CH ₃ (C23)
								1363	1323	ρC20-H40
					1351	1320	wagCH ₂ (C12)	1351	1321	wagCH ₂ (C12)
		1359	1317	ρ'C22-H43				1350	1311	ρ'C22-H43
		1349	1315	ρCH ₂ (C24),	1350	1315	ρC11-H29			
1314 s		1348	1312	δ(O4H52)						
		1337	1304	ρC11-H29	1345	1309	ρC14-H34			
		1333	1300	ρC15-H35				1348	1310	ρ'C18-H39
					1338	1305	ρCH ₂ (C24)	1341	1307	ρCH ₂ (C24)
	1298 m	1323	1295	wagCH ₂ (C12)	1334	1297	ρ'C14-H34			
					1325	1292	ρ'C18-H39	1330	1295	ρC14-H34
								1324	1286	vN9-C19
		1310	1285	wagCH ₂ (C17) ρ'C10-H28	1316	1284	wagCH ₂ (C17) ρ'C10-H28	1316	1284	wagCH ₂ (C17) ρ'C10-H28
		1310	1276	ρ'C18-H39 ρ'C21-H42	1310	1281	ρ'C15-H35	1309	1282	ρ'C11-H29
		1300	1263	ρCH ₂ (C12)	1306	1269	ρCH ₂ (C13)	1301	1265	ρ'C21-H42
1259 s	1263 m	1296	1262	ρC14-H34	1289	1257	ρ'C11-H29	1293	1259	ρCH ₂ (C13)
		1280	1248	ρC22-H43	1287	1253	ρC22-H43	1292	1253	ρC22-H43
								1285	1250	ρC15-H35
					1281	1246	vN9-C19			
	1235 w	1266	1232	ρ'C20-H40	1271	1232	ρ'C21-H42	1281	1248	ρ'C20-H40
					1266	1225	δ(O4H52)	1269	1229	ρ'C14-H34; δ(O4H52)
1217 sh	1221 w	1257	1218	ρ'CH ₃ (C23)	1264	1219	ρCH ₂ (C17)	1267	1221	ρCH ₂ (C17)
		1249	1209	vN9-C19	1244	1203	δ(O6H57)			
	1198 vw	1246	1199	ρCH ₂ (C17)						
1198 sh	1189 w	1236	1189	δ(O5H53)				1234	1184	δ(O5H53)
		1226	1178	vN8-C23	1225	1178	ρCH ₂ (C12)	1233	1183	ρCH ₂ (C12)
	1171 w	1224	1177	δ(O6H57)						
1168sh					1210	1165	ρ'CH ₃ (C23)	1211	1179	ρ'CH ₃ (C23)
1151 m	1155 w	1193	1156	ρCH ₂ (C13)	1197	1158	δ(O5H53)			
	1148 m				1173	1141	ρ'CH ₃ (C26)	1172	1140	ρ'CH ₃ (C26)
1135 sh	1137 m	1176	1139	vN9-C15 vC15-C22	1155	1121	vN9-C15 vC15-C22	1159	1124	vN9-C15 vC15-C22
1128 sh	1123 m	1158	1122	ρCH ₃ (C23)						
		1153	1118	ρ'CH ₃ (C26)						
		1148	1109	vC16-O4						
1101 m	1090 s	1147	1101	vC20-O6				1154	1116	vC20-O6
		1135	1098	vC22-C25	1149	1105	vC22-C25	1152	1105	vC22-C25

		1131	1093	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$	1138	1100	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$	1139	1102	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$
					1129	1093	vC20-O6	1135	1098	vC16-O4
		1121	1082	vC14-C16	1127	1089	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$	1130	1092	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$
1084 s		1108	1068	vC14-O3	1123	1085	vC16-O4			
					1110	1073	vC10-C17	1109	1071	vC10-C17
		1100	1064	vC18-O5	1107	1070	vC14-O3	1100	1068	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$,
		1093	1056	vC10-C17	1099	1066	vC14-C16	1092	1056	vC21-O3; vC14-O3
1046 s	1051 m				1082	1047	vC18-O5	1083	1047	vC18-C20
		1083	1044	vC10-C13	1075	1036	vC10-C13	1080	1040	vC10-C13
	1033 w	1071	1033	vC11-C12						
1025 sh		1069	1032	vC21-O3	1067	1029	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$	1062	1026	vC18-O5
					1063	1021	vC24-C26	1060	1022	vC14-C16
		1049	1015	vC15-C14	1049	1016	vC15-C14	1052	1019	vC24-C26
		1045	1007	vC24-C26				1048	1010	vC11-C12
996 m	998 w	1034	1000	vN8-C11	1044	1005	vN8-C23	1040	1000	vN8-C23
					1040	1001	vC11-C12	1025	992	vC15-C14
	987 w	1029	992	vN8-C13	1030	995	vC21-O3 vC18-C20			
		1022	980	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	1009	980	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	1013	980	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$
	974 vw	1005	977	vC18-C20				1006	972	vC11-C19
972 m		999	970	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	1007	971	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$	995	969	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$
960 m	959 vw	996	966	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$,	1001	967	vC11-C19			
		985	951	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$	993	966	$\rho\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	993	962	$\rho'\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$
922w	941 w	964	935	$\beta\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$						
					985	954	vN9-C15	984	952	vN8-C11
		941	907	vC11-C19						
					965	935	vN8-C11	966	937	vN8-C13
	923 w	923	889	$\delta \text{C}19\text{N}9\text{H}15$	948	916	$\delta \text{C}19\text{N}9\text{H}15$	946	915	$\delta \text{C}19\text{N}9\text{H}15$
901w	907 w				933	903	vN8-C13	933	907	$\delta \text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$
882 w	884 m	914	886	vC17-C24	923	887	vC17-C24	922	888	$\beta\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$,
873 m					911	882	$\beta\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$	912	885	vC17-C24
862 m	867 w	905	872	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}13)$	901	872	$\delta \text{N}8\text{-C}11\text{-C}19$	904	874	$\delta \text{N}8\text{C}11\text{C}19$
	856 w	902	864	vC10-C12						
		889	849	vC20-C21	892	850	vC20-C21	895	858	vC20-C21
832w	842 m	875	846	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}12)$				890	847	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}12)$ vC10-C12
815 m	813 w	852	813	vC16-C18	884	845	vC10-C12			
811 sh					873	830	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}13)$	877	831	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}13)$
801 m	801 vw				844	807	vC16-C18	844	809	vC16-C18
		829	793	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}17)$	825	792	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}17)$	827	797	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}17)$
	784 vw	782	766	$\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}21$ $\delta\text{C}20\text{C}21\text{S}2$	783	769	$\delta\text{C}20\text{C}21\text{S}2$ $\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}21$	787	771	$\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}21$ $\delta\text{C}20\text{C}21\text{S}2$
	767 vw							779	767	$\gamma \text{N}9\text{-H}41$
738w		761	742	$\gamma \text{C}19=\text{O}7$	764	738	$\tau\text{wCH}_2(\text{C}12)$	754	736	$\gamma \text{C}19=\text{O}7$

724w	722 s	750	712	$\delta N9C15C14$				749	712	$\tau O6-H57$
699 sh	709 s	730	692	$\beta C19=O7$	754	691	$\delta N9C15C14$	723	690	$\delta C14C15C22$
690 m		715	687	$\nu C27-S2$	712	685	$\nu C27-S2$	715	688	$\nu C27-S2$
					705	681	$\delta N9C15C22$			
	678 s	709	678	$\tau wCH_2(C24)$	691	680	$\tau wCH_2(C24)$	704	681	$\tau wCH_2(C24)$
								684	672	$\delta O5C18C16$ $\delta N9C15C22$
		681	668	$\tau O4-H52$	677	660	$\gamma N9-H41$; $\beta C19=O7$	678	661	$\beta C19=O7$
644 s	650 vs	661	652	$\delta N9C15C22$	659	652	$\delta O5C18C16$			
		639	629	$\delta O5C18C16$	631	620	$\delta C15C14O3$	646	633	$\delta C15C14O3$
		636	622	$\beta R1 (A5)$	609	594	$\gamma C19=O7$			
595 m	607 w	602	595	$\gamma N9-H41$	585	575	$\beta R2 (A5)$ $\beta R1 (A5)$	618	604	$\beta R1 (A5)$
		589	578	$\beta R2 (A5)$	584	572	$\nu C21-S2$	595	585	$\beta R2 (A5)$,
568 m		579	568	$\nu C21-S2$	573	563	$\nu C22-Cl1$	591	580	$\nu C21-S2$
		560	551	$\nu C22-Cl1$	539	532	$\beta R2 (A6)$	578	566	$\nu C22-Cl1$
	543 vw				520	513	$\tau O4-H52$	545	538	$\beta R2 (A6)$
520 m	527 w							520	513	$\tau O4-H52$
516 w		519	511	$\beta R2 (A6)$						
477 w	484 s				488	478	$\gamma N8-C23$	495	486	$\gamma N8-C23$
	467 m	463	457	$\delta O5C18C20$	463	457	$\delta O5C18C20$	466	459	$\delta O5C18C20$
452 w	447 w	457	450	$\delta O4C16C14$	457	451	$\delta C11C19N9$	465	458	$\delta C11C19N9$
	432 vw	445	436	$\delta C17C10C13$	442	429	$\delta C17C10C13$	436	423	$\delta C17C10C13$
419 w	410 w	426	419	$\delta C17C10C12$	427	421	$\delta C17C10C12$	426	421	$\delta C17C10C12$
	395 s	375	370	$\delta C11C19N9$						
	365 s	371	366	$\delta Cl1C22C25$						
					368	365	$\delta O4C16C14$	380	376	$\delta O4C16C14$
		351	345	$\delta O3C21S2$	358	353	$\delta O3C21S2$	354	349	$\delta O3C21S2$
	340 s	347	342	$\gamma N8-C23$				347	345	$\beta R3 (A6)$
					339	335	$\delta Cl1C22C25$	337	332	$\delta Cl1C22C25$
	322 w	325	321	$\beta R3 (A6)$	333	328	$\beta R3 (A6)$			
					321	316	$\tau O5-H53$			
	314 m	319	312	$\delta C15C22C25$	317	313	$\delta C17C24C26$	322	316	$\delta C17C24C26$
		305	300	$\delta C17C24C26$	304	300	$\delta C19N9C15$	311	305	$\delta C19N9C15$
		297	291	$\beta N8-C23$				300	295	$\delta C15C22C25$
					293	289	$\tau O6-H57$			
	285 vw	286	282	$\delta O4C16C18$	284	281	$\delta O4C16C18$	293	289	$\delta O4C16C18$
					280	277	$\beta N8-C23$	288	284	$\beta N8-C23$
	268 w	270	266	$\delta C12C11C19$	272	267	$\delta C15C22C25$	271	267	$\delta N9C15C14$
		259	255	$\tau O6-H57$						
		253	252	$\delta C21S2C27$	255	250	$\delta C21S2C27$	268	264	$\tau C22C15N9C19$
								254	250	$\tau O5-H53$
	245 s	248	235	$\delta C11C19N9$	253	246	$\delta C12-C11-C19$	250	238	$\delta C12-C11-C19$

		244	224	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$	248	230	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$	250	231	$\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}18$
		239	220	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$	242	223	$\beta\text{R}3 (\text{A}6)$	243	226	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$
		232	217	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}25)$	234	215	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$	235	222	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}26)$
	213 m	214	210	$\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}18$	221	212	$\delta\text{O}6\text{C}20\text{C}18$			
		207	200	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$	214	207	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$			
	197 m	201	198	$\delta\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$	195	192	$\delta\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$	215	199	$\delta\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$
	183 m	190	187	$\delta\text{C}11\text{C}22\text{C}15$				200	196	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}23)$
		178	176	$\tau\text{O}5\text{-H}53$	182	178	$\delta\text{C}11\text{C}22\text{C}15$	184	181	$\delta\text{C}11\text{C}22\text{C}15$
		173	168	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}5)$	168	165	$\delta\text{C}10\text{C}17\text{C}24$	170	168	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}5)$ $\delta\text{C}10\text{C}17\text{C}24$
		160	151	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}6)$				163	153	$\delta\text{C}21\text{S}2\text{C}27$
		157	145	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	147	138	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$	156	141	$\tau_w\text{CH}_3(\text{C}27)$
		136	132	$\tau\text{R}3(\text{A}6)$	139	136	$\delta\text{C}14\text{C}15\text{C}22$	142	132	$\tau\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{N}9\text{C}19$
		133	126	$\delta\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{O}3$				134	129	$\tau\text{R}3(\text{A}6)$
					124	119	$\delta\text{C}20\text{C}21\text{S}2$	122	118	$\nu\text{H}61\text{-Cl}62$
		117	113	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$	121	118	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$	120	114	$\delta\text{C}14\text{C}15\text{C}22$
		102	98	$\delta\text{C}10\text{C}17\text{C}24$	105	97	$\tau\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{N}9\text{C}19$	104	101	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}6)$
		101	97	$\tau\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{N}9\text{C}19$	96	92	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}5)$	103	96	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}5)$
		91	85	$\delta\text{C}14\text{C}15\text{C}22$	90	85	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}12$	97	89	$\tau\text{O}7\text{C}19\text{C}11\text{C}12$
		80	74	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}12$	80	74	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}12$ $\tau\text{C}26\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10$	81	75	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}6)$
		77	70	$\tau\text{C}26\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10$				78	72	$\tau\text{C}26\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10$
		70	65	$\tau\text{C}27\text{S}2\text{C}21\text{O}3$	72	67	$\tau\text{C}26\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10$	63	60	$\delta\text{N}8\text{-H}61\text{-Cl}62$
		65	62	$\tau\text{R}3(\text{A}6)$	63	60	$\tau\text{R}1 (\text{A}5)$	61	56	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}12$
					62	58	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}6)$	57	53	$\tau\text{C}27\text{S}2\text{C}21\text{O}3$
		52						51	48	$\tau\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{N}9\text{C}19$
		52	48	$\tau\text{C}25\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{C}14$				48	45	$\tau\text{C}11\text{N}8\text{H}61\text{Cl}62$
		43	40	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}15$	44	40	$\tau\text{C}27\text{S}2\text{C}21\text{O}3$			
					41	38	$\tau\text{C}25\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{C}14$	37	35	$\tau\text{C}25\text{C}22\text{C}15\text{C}14$
					33	32	$\tau\text{R}3(\text{A}6)$			
		27	25	$\tau\text{N}9\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$				22	21	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}15$
		19	18	$\tau\text{R}2 (\text{A}5)$	20	18	$\tau\text{N}9\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$	20	18	$\tau\text{N}9\text{C}15\text{C}14\text{C}16$
					15	14	$\tau\text{C}24\text{C}17\text{C}10\text{C}15$	15	14	$\delta\text{N}8\text{-H}61\text{-Cl}62$
		12	11	$\tau\text{O}7\text{C}19\text{C}11\text{C}12$	13	12	$\tau\text{O}7\text{C}19\text{C}11\text{C}12$			

Abbreviations: ν , stretching; β deformation in the plane; γ deformation out of plane; wag, wagging; τ torsion; β_R , deformation ring τ_R , torsion ring; ρ , rocking; τ_w , twisting; δ , deformation; a, antisymmetric; s, symmetric; (A₁), Ring1; (A₂), Ring2; ^aThis work, ^bFrom scaled quantum mechanics force field.

Source: ^cFrom Infrared Reference Spectra. (n.d.); ^dFrom SpectraBase. (n.d.).

Bands Assignments

OH modes. Calculations predict the three OH stretching modes for the species of clindamycin

around 3617 and 3312 cm⁻¹. Hence, the weak and strong IR band at 3748 and 3386 cm⁻¹, respectively are assigned to those vibration modes of CA and HCl species while for FB the

intense IR band at 3282 cm^{-1} is assigned to other OH stretching mode, as reported for similar compounds (Rudyk, et al., 2019). The IR bands at 1425 and 1314 cm^{-1} and the shoulder at 1198 cm^{-1} are assigned to the OH in-plane deformation modes, as observed in Table 12. Note that the O6-H57 deformation mode in the hydrochloride is assigned to 1424 cm^{-1} , while for the other species at lower wavenumbers. That difference is justified because the OH group is involved in a halogen bond with the chlorine atom additional. The corresponding out-of-plane deformation modes are associated with the weak bands at 724 and 520 cm^{-1} .

NH modes. The strong IR band at 3386 cm^{-1} is assigned to N-H stretching modes for the FB and CA forms, while for the HCl this mode is associated to the band at 3282 cm^{-1} (see Table 3) due to H bond that this group form with the chlorine atom. Calculations predict those modes for the FB and CA forms at 3457 and 3398 cm^{-1} , respectively; while for the HCl that mode is predicted at 3116 cm^{-1} . The in-plane deformations modes are related to the band at 1555 cm^{-1} , while the out-the plane deformations are associated to shoulder at 598 cm^{-1} , in agreement with similar compounds (Romano, Davies, & Brandán, 2017).

CH₃ modes. The two stretching modes of methyl groups are associated to the bands at 3067 , 3031 and 2924 cm^{-1} because these modes are predicted between 3116 and 2920 cm^{-1} . The two CH₃ deformations modes are predicted between 1473 and 1380 cm^{-1} ; hence, they are assigned in this region (IR: 1466 and 1452 cm^{-1}). Additionally one of these modes is predicted by calculations between 1326 and 1327 , hence, it is assigned to shoulder at 1329 cm^{-1} . Also, the rocking and twisting modes are predicted as in similar species (Romano, Davies, & Brandán, 2017; Vakili, et al., 2021; Darugar, et al., 2022) and, thus, they were assigned in those regions.

CH modes. The bands at 2992 , 2907 , 2865 and 2860 cm^{-1} are easily assigned to C-H stretching modes because they are supported by the values obtained through the calculations. The other C-H modes were predicted and assigned in the expected regions for this group (Romano,

Davies, & Brandán, 2017; Vakili, et al., 2021; Darugar, et al., 2022), as observed in Table 12.

CH₂ modes. The IR bands at 2958 , 2924 and 2688 cm^{-1} are assigned to the stretching modes of these groups, while the CH₂ bending modes are associated with the shoulder at 1505 cm^{-1} . Calculations predict the stretching modes between 3029 and 2789 cm^{-1} while the bending modes between 1481 and 1443 cm^{-1} although they appear overlapped with signals corresponding to methyl group. For all species, wagging modes are predicted between 1400 - 1240 cm^{-1} , while rocking modes between 1315 and 1156 cm^{-1} . Hence, the IR band at 1217 cm^{-1} is assigned to rocking modes of three species, as indicated in Table 12.

C=O modes. The strong IR band at 1686 cm^{-1} is easily assigned to stretching modes ($\nu_{\text{C=O}}$), while the shoulder at 699 cm^{-1} and the weak band at 738 cm^{-1} are assigned to in-plane ($\beta_{\text{C=O}}$) and out-of-plane ($\gamma_{\text{C=O}}$) deformation modes, respectively. Calculations predict for the three species the $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ at 1679 , 1705 and 1689 cm^{-1} ; $\beta_{\text{C=O}}$ at 692 , 660 and 661 and the $\gamma_{\text{C=O}}$ at 742 , 594 and 736 cm^{-1} , respectively (Rudyk, et al., 2019).

S-C modes. SQM calculations predict the S2-C21 stretching modes between 568 - 580 cm^{-1} and for S2-C27 between 685 and 688 cm^{-1} . Therefore, the IR bands of media intensities at 568 and 690 cm^{-1} can be assigned to those vibrational modes. On the other hand, the deformation modes (δ_{C21S2C27}) are predicted at low wavenumbers for the free base and cationic forms respectively at 252 and 250 cm^{-1} , while for the hydrochloride it is predicted at 153 cm^{-1} .

C-Cl modes: Calculations predict these stretching modes of FB, CA and HCl species at 551 , 563 y 566 cm^{-1} , very close to the S2-C21 stretching modes; while the C11-C22-C15 deformations are predicted in the three species at 366 , 335 and 332 , respectively. In clonidine hydrochloride (Chlorine bound to the ring) was assigned to 421 and 402 cm^{-1} (Romano, Davies, & Brandán, 2017).

Force Field

As in above works reported by our investigation group, the scaled force constants of three forms have been calculated from harmonic FFs using

the Molvib program (Rauhut, & Pulay, 1995; Sundius, 2002). The results for all forms of clindamycin in gas phase by using the B3LY/6-31G* method are presented in Table 13.

Table 13. Scaled Force Constants for Free Base, Cationic and Hydrochloride Species of Clindamycin in Phase Gas by Using the B3LYP/6-31G* Method

Description	B3LYP/6-31G*		
	Free base	Cation	Hydrochloride
$f(\nu O-H)$	7.014	7.155	6.549
$f(\nu N-H)$	6.632	5.505	5.433
$f(\nu C=O)$	10.752	10.646	10.459
$f(\nu C-O)$	4.766	4.713	4.754
$f(\nu N-C)$	5.052	4.788	5.066
$f(\nu C-S)$	2.881	2.870	2.868
$f(\nu CH_3)$	4.860	4.961	4.937
$f(\nu CH_2)_{Ring}$	4.701	4.916	4.902
$f(\nu CH_2)$	4.685	4.709	4.709
$f(\nu C-C)_{Ring}$	3.863	3.833	3.959
$f(\nu C-C)$	3.986	3.980	4.013
$f(\nu C-Cl)$	2.478	2.585	2.588
$f(\nu C-H)$	--	--	0.241
$f(\delta OH)$	0.771	0.790	0.817
$f(\delta CH_2)$	0.769	0.766	0.766
$f(\delta CH_3)$	0.556	0.552	0.551
$f(\delta C21S2C27)$	1.169	1.069	1.149

Note: Units in $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA}^{-1}$ for stretching and $\text{mdyn } \text{\AA} \text{ rad}^{-2}$ for angle deformations

Abbreviations: ν , stretching; δ deformation in the plane.

That table shows that the hydrochloride species presents low values of both $f(\nu O-H)$ and $f(\nu N-H)$ force constants because in this species the OH and NH groups are involved in the formation of H bonds. For the same reason, the $f(\nu C=O)$ also presents a low value in that species, as compared with FB and CA species. The variations that present the other force constants are related to structural differences, such as those associated to CH_2 groups of rings and side chain, which are $f(\nu CH_2)_{Ring}$ and $f(\nu CH_2)$ force constants, respectively. Because in general those groups in the rings are more restricted to move and, hence, the values of those constants are higher than the corresponding to the of side chain. The

remaining constants present few changes in the three species.

Conclusions

In this research, the structures, topological and vibrational properties of three forms of lincosamide antibiotic clindamycin have been studied combining mechanical-quantum calculations with the SQMFF methodology while the water effects on the properties were analysed by using SCRF calculations and the IEFPCM model. Additional NBO and AIM calculations were accomplished for all species of antibiotic in both media. The hydrochloride species has revealed a higher solvation energy of

-301.83 kJ/mol similar to reported for the hydrobromide species of alkaloid scopolamine (-309.19 kJ/mol). NBO studies show different $n \rightarrow \sigma^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions while the AIM calculations evidence the following H bonds: C-O $\cdots$ H, N-H $\cdots$ O, O-H $\cdots$ O, O-H $\cdots$ Cl, C-H $\cdots$ Cl and N-H $\cdots$ Cl interactions. Frontier orbitals calculations suggest that HCl is the most reactive form of clindamycin. In addition, the 174, 177 and 180 normal vibration modes expected for FB, CA and HCl species have been assigned in complete form and its scaled force constants reported for first time.

Ethics Approval and Consent to participate

Ethics approval 'Not applicable'

Consent for Publication

The authors declare consent for publication.

Availability of Data and Materials

Available when the authors require it.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Author Contributions

Elida Romano: prepared figures and tables, Silvia Antonia Brandán: wrote the main manuscript text.

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